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THE LANGUAGE OF POETIC TEXT AND THE LINGUOPOETIC VALUE OF INTERTEXTUALITY

Gulnoza Sabirova

Urgench state university named after Abu Raykhon Beruni
Foreign languages faculty, Teacher of English language and literature
department

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Abstract: The poem differentiates with its linguistic style, as its brevity and simple. The poets try to pick the words in poems according to the degree of impressiveness and informativity. In this way, in expressing ideas shortly and impressively, poets rely on powerful tools in language as intertextuality.

Абстрактный: Стихотворение отличается своим лингвистическим стилем, краткостью и простотой. Поэты стараются подбирать слова в стихах в соответствии со степенью выразительности и информативности. Таким образом, выражая свои мысли кратко и выразительно, поэты опираются на интертекстуальность и другие мощные языковые инструменты. Лингвопоэтические особенности играют решающую роль в создании содержательных стихотворений. Для выявления лингвопоэтических единиц в науке необходим контекстуальный анализ.

Key words: poem, poetic text, linguopoetic features, intertextuality, poetic language.

Ключевые слова: стихотворение, поэтический текст, лингвопоэтические особенности, интертекстуальность, поэтический язык.

Introduction.

The poetic text is distinguished by its brevity in form, and by its melodiousness in art, and by its beautiful expression of the state of mind through wordplay. Linguistic-poetic features in poetry are understood, first of all, as the harmony of language and poetics, imagery in poetic speech, semantic development, layers of meaning, rhythm, melody, harmony of sound, metaphor, epithet, personification, alliteration, assonance, etc. These features distinguish the poetic text from other literary genres, give it a bright

national character and artistry. Poetic language provides its own imagery and scope of meaning.

The words used in poetry often have symbolic, metaphorical, and emotional equivalents, and words, as an artistic tool, play an important role in revealing the essence of various works. Therefore, poetry contains more poetic words, lexical units, figurative combinations, and symbolic meanings. These aspects are also among the indicators that determine the linguopoetic nature of a poetic text. A deeper analysis of the linguopoetic features of a poetic text reveals the effective use of the lexical, phraseological, grammatical, and stylistic capabilities of the language for artistic purposes. In this context, the external and internal structure of the poetic text, its primary and secondary layers, semantic connections, tone and rhythm, and the creation of artistic images are also taken into account. The harmonious use of language and poetics in poetry creates an artistic effect and aesthetic pleasure.

If we look at the history of the term Linguopoetics⁸, it is a combination of the words “linguistics” and “poetics” and is recognized as one of the developing fields of linguistics. The history of Linguopoetics dates back to the time of Aristotle, who in his famous work “Poetics” provides detailed information about the poetic arts, especially poetic genres. In this work, in addition to providing information about various genres of poetry, he also discusses the art of poetry.

M. Yuldashev, who has fully studied the problem of linguopoetics of a literary text based on Uzbek language materials, points out the following main features of linguopoetic analysis:

1. An approach based on the unity of form and content; In such an approach, form and content should consistently complement each other
2. Proceeding from the unity of space and time; that is, the space and time given in the text must always be in the same time and duration.
3. Evaluation based on the relationship between the language in daily usage and the literary language; giving a general assessment of the language without going

⁸ lingvopoetika tushunchasi va uning o'zbek tilshunosligida eurasian journal of academic research O'rganilishi jumag'ulova Xusniya Maxmarosul qizi

beyond the standard language framework

4. Approach to the literary text as an artistic-aesthetic whole; be able to create an artistic aesthetic unity from the elements used in the text;

5. Identify poetically actualized language means in the literary text;

6. Determine the ratio of explicitness and implicitness in the literary text;

7. Identification of linguistic and semantic features of intertextuality mechanisms in a literary text.

The researcher emphasizes that the identification of poetically actualized language means in a literary text is one of the important principles in linguopoetic analysis, because by revealing the linguistic and artistic essence of such means, one can clearly imagine the mechanisms of formation and use of artistic content. Indeed, this principle is convenient in directly determining and assessing the aesthetic value of a literary text and can also serve as a basis for working on the basis of other principles. Moreover, being able to imagine linguistic art on the basis of this principle is also useful for a novice analyst.

We use different examples of intertextuality frequently in common speech, such as allusions like the following:⁹

- He was lying so obviously, you could almost see his nose growing.
- He's asking her to the prom. It's like a happy version of Romeo and Juliet.
- It's hard being an adult! Peter Pan had the right idea.

The concept of intertextuality can also be expanded to music, film, advertising, and so on in the way that everything produced now is influenced by what came before. References to pop culture in advertising, films that are made from books, and diss tracks in rap can all be considered intertextual, though they are not strictly texts.

Intertextuality play an important role in creating new texts. If we take poems as an example, poems should consist of some units of other texts created before. Everything has some ground either abstract or concrete. In this regard, 'intertextual' approach looks sound and is one of the useful ways of reading, writing, and analyzing

2. <https://literarydevices.com/intertextuality>

a particular text. The term 'intertextuality' refers to the potential of texts which knowingly or unknowingly bear references and influences, echoes and allusions, styles and norms, and even sometimes revisions of themes and contexts from numerous centers. The term appears a little novel but the assumptions implied by; are quite old. A text is a matrix of several texts. No text can be interpreted without taking recourse of other extant by-gone works. It is quite natural. While reading a literary piece of art few other texts are reminded of automatically¹⁰.

Some intertextual units are commonly used in literary works as carrying cultural and national value in people's life. These units can be national heroes' names, quotes, historical events, places or sometimes names of famous literary works. We will introduce a poem of local poet Kamil Khorezmy¹¹ in Khorezm who used many names of historical heroes in Uzbekistan.

a) Raise the banner of the holy Quran.

The Amir has given birth to Sahibqiran,
The Sahibqiran's heart is clearly in your face,
Uzbekistan, be present in the world!

Here the name of Amir Sahibqiran is the popular name of Tamerlane in the world.

a) Seeking medicine from the motherland,
The world's porch of Babur has become narrow,
The field of poetry has opened its arms to him,
The magic of Shah's poetry is on your joyful face
Uzbekistan, be on your world's face!

In this poem Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur, the founder of Baburi dynasty in India, is described.

b) Al-Khwarizmi composed "al-jabr" in the world,
Bashar expanded his thinking, ...

Al-Khwarizmi was famous scientist and founder of a science algebra over the

3. https://www.academia.edu/35928661/Intertextuality_the_way_of_reading_and_writing. Raj Kumar Mishra

4. Kamil Avaz. O'tayotgan vaqt. – T.; "Yangi asr avlodi", 2006. – 258 bet.

world.

- c) The secret of the world is abundant in Sina,
The world has found its medicine in your face,
Uzbekistan, be the world in your face!

In this line the poet informs proudly about Sina's findings in medicine.

Conclusion.

In writing poems, poetic style should be professional with its informavity and impressiveness. In this case poetic features play a crucial role. While expressing ideas shortly and correctly, some poets use intertextual units in their poems. These intertextual units remind readers historical events or important history and make easier readers to understand the idea.

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